

Complete genome sequence of *Erwinia* sp STN24 a novel strain bacterium isolated from wheat seeds, a potential bacterial exopolysaccharides producer

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Abstract

In recent decades, demands of natural polymers, especially extracellular polysaccharides (EPS), has attracted increasing attention due to their useful physicochemical properties and diverse functionalities. In this context, the present study aimed to isolate a new strain with high EPS production. We report the analysis of an annotated complete genome assembly of an *Erwinia* sp ST24 strain isolated from wheat seeds. This genome assembly consists of 4678025 bp, including 4265 protein-coding sequences, 91 tRNAs, 1 tmRNA, and 55.89% GC content. The complete genome sequence of *Erwinia* strain can be used to understand and manipulate phenotypic behavior and extracellular polysaccharide production for biotechnological applications.

Introduction

The *Erwinia* genus is part of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family. They are Gram-negative, non-spore forming rod-shaped, facultatively anaerobic, with peritrichous flagella (Aremu and Babalola 2015). For the past several decades, some *Erwinia* species that are harmful to pome fruit trees have been described, these include *E. pyrifoliae*, Japanese *Erwinia* spp. that cause bacterial illnesses of pears (Palacio-Bielsa et al. 2012) and other non-pathogenic *Erwinia* species, like *E. billingiae* and *E. tasmaniensis*, are discovered in the same hosts. While these species share genetic and phenotypic similarities, they can be differentiated based on taxonomic criteria, resulting in the classification of 20 validly named species within the *Erwinia* genus (as per <https://lpsn.dsmz.de/genus/erwinia>) (Llop, 2015 ; Tao et al. 2023).

Numerous microorganisms sourced from diverse environments ranging from the deep sea, salt lakes, soil, milk, wine, and diverse plant components like roots, leaves, and fruits are isolated to generate a wide array of specific active compounds in extreme environments, such as exopolysaccharides (EPS) (Niknezhad et al. 2018).

EPS have attracted scientific interest because of their distinct structure, properties, and potential applications across a spectrum of scientific, industrial, medical, and technological fields. Their intricate and diverse structure imparts them with exclusive biological activities and functions

(Netrusov et al. 2023; Qi et al. 2022). This study aimed to sequence, assemble, and annotate the *Erwinia* sp. ST24 genome in order to perform evolutionary research and find new bioactive compounds.

Materiel et Methods

Bacterial isolation

Erwinia sp strain STN24 isolated from wheat seeds was used in this study. The strain has been grown in Luria Bertani liquid medium at 37°C for 18 h with moderate shaking and the cells were used for genomic extraction.

Whole-Genome sequencing

The sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA involved a number of processes. Briefly, genomic DNA sample were extracted by Microbes NG from the isolated bacteria and they were quantified using the Quant-iT dsDNA HS kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) assay on an Eppendorf AF2200 plate reader. Sequencing libraries were then generated using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA). Then Read trimming was carried out using Trimmomatic version 0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014) removing the sequence adaptor with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15 and assembly were performed employing SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al. 2012), these contigs were finally annotated using Prokka 1.11(Seemann 2014). The DNA extraction, whole-genome sequencing, genome assembly and annotation were conducted by MicrobesNG. Their established techniques are available at <https://microbesng.com/>.

Results

Genomic description

The genomic features of *Erwinia* sp. STN 24 are shown in Table1. The complete genome contains 4,7 Mb with a mean coverage of 64 and the C+G content was 55.89 %. The total number of genes, including 4265 protein coding genes, 55 types of tRNA and one cluster of tmRNA. The findings from the Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) test, along with the current taxonomic nomenclature, revealed a genetic match of over 99% between the submitted genome sequence and the *Erwinia* genus.

Nucleotide sequence accession number

The complete genome sequence of the *Erwinia* sp. STN24 strain has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank with the accession number listed in Table 1.

Acknowledgments

Support for sequencing the bacterial strains was provided by GetGenome and The Sainsbury Laboratory, Norwich, UK, with contributions from the Gatsby Charitable Foundation, the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC), and The University of East Anglia. Our thanks go to Professor Sophien Kamoun for his role in developing GetGenome, and we express our appreciation to Dr. James Canham and Dr. Joe Win for their technical assistance.

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Table 1: Genomic features of *Erwinia* strain STN24 assembled from Illumina reads.

	<i>Erwinia</i> sp. STN24
Genomic size (bp)	4678025
Total numbers of contigs	54
Number of contigs >1000 bp	17
Largest contig (bp)	2126813
Mean coverage (X)	64
GC content (%)	55.89
N50 (bp)	508976
N75 (bp)	429254
L50 (bp)	2
L75 (bp)	4
CRISPRs	3
tRNA	91
tmRNA	1
Protein coding genes	4265
Biosample	SAMN42420799
GenBank accession Number	JBGGPM000000000
SRA accession Number	SRR29775610